

PHARMACOEPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PERFORMED CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT IN PATIENTS WITH CHOLELITHIASIS OF THE GERONTOLOGICAL GROUP OF FERGANA

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Relevance. According to the WHO, in the modern treatment and diagnostic process of cholelithiasis (CSD) it is important, especially in individuals of the gerontological group (75-90 years and above), not only to provide scientific information on a certain type of treatment (surgical or conservative) and clinical and fundamental recommendations, but also to acquire modern innovative technologies acceptable for preventive surgery and the ability to use them. For the advanced development of CSD surgery in the 21st century, it is important to identify the most susceptible individuals with high or very high risk for this pathology and their special prevention to ensure the process of early detection, effective and safe treatment (with proper pharmacovigilance, pharmacoepidemiological screening) and the prevention of not only CSD itself, but also formidable complications of cholecystectomy, cholecystostomy, choledochotomy, choledochomyotomy and transduodenal sphincteropylotomy.

The aim of the study is to study the prevalence, pharmacoepidemiology of cholelithiasis and its main risk factors among the male and female unorganized population of the gerontological group of the Fergana Valley to enable scientifically based planning and optimization of early diagnosis, prevention and treatment of this disease.

The object of the study was a contingent of 4,500 individuals of the gerontological age population, formed using random number tables based on the nominal electoral lists of men and women in three regions of the Fergana Valley; as well as 779 patients with cholelithiasis who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the regional multidisciplinary hospitals of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana (for VEN analysis).

The subject of the study: were the results of general clinical and biochemical blood tests, survey, physical, instrumental and

pharmacoepidemiological monitoring; as well as the method of "daily nutrition reproduction" adapted to the peculiarities of Uzbek cuisine.

Research methods. To solve the set tasks, epidemiological, clinical, laboratory, biochemical, instrumental, pharmacoepidemiological and statistical research methods were used, as well as the "daily nutrition reproduction" method.

Results of the study: In the regional surgical hospitals of Fergana, for the treatment of cholelithiasis in gerontologically aged individuals, the corresponding conservative therapy with basic drugs is used with the following frequency levels: antihypertensive drugs - 8.4% (in the total number of those examined with cholelithiasis), 0.0% (in women) and 8.4% (in men), antispasmodics - 14.0%, 1.12% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=35.28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$), analgesics - 14.0%, 11.2% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=3.5,28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$), antibacterial drugs - 14.0%, 1.12% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=35.28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$), enzyme inhibitors - 14.0%, 1.12% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=3.5,28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$), infusion agents - 14.0%, 1.12% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=35.28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$), NSAIDs - 4.5%, 0.56% and 3.9% ($\chi^2=0.324$; $P>0.05$; $RR=1.643$; 95% $CI=0.360-7.492$), anticoagulants - 14.0%, 1.12% and 12.9% ($\chi^2=35.28$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.087$; 95% $CI=0.023-0.330$) and proton blockers - 2.8%, 0.56% and 2.2% ($\chi^2=1.223$; $P>0.05$; $RR=2.875$; 95% $CI=0.554-14.93$). Conservative treatment is performed in 92.1% of women and 7.9% of men with cholelithiasis [$\chi^2=252.8$; $P<0.001$; $RR=0.085$; 95% $CI=0.052-0.141$]. The analysis showed that in Fergana hospitals, the rationality of treating cholelithiasis in the gerontological population ($\geq 60-90$ years) is 95.0%, and compliance with international clinical guidelines is 96%. The risk of developing pre- and postoperative complications is 4-5%, or the risk of such in gerontological patients remains despite conservative therapy

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